

Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) analysis utilizing the FFT capabilities of modern digital storage oscilloscopes

Sebastian Westerhold¹

¹Independent Researcher, Baltic Lab, Kiel, Germany

E-mail: sebastian@baltic-lab.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7965-3140>

Abstract

This paper shows how to analyze Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) using the fast Fourier transformation (FFT) capability of low-cost digital sampling oscilloscopes. It was found that THD measurements using this method are accurate within less than a few percent of absolute error. A high level of accuracy can be achieved as long as the measured THD is sufficiently large (> 3.2 %) in order to not subceed the dynamic range of common 8-bit digital storage oscilloscopes. The method presented herein is particularly convenient if only a coarse, relative indicator of THD improvement or degradation is needed.

Keywords: THD, THD-F, Total Harmonic Distortion, FFT, Oscilloscope

1. Introduction

Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) is an important characteristic of audio, radio frequency and power systems related circuits. It is an important measure because the value gives insight into linearity and spectral purity of a system. Specialized THD analyzers are usually used in a laboratory setting to determine the THD characteristics of a device under test (DUT).

THD is an umbrella term used for various different standards of total harmonic distortion measurement. The method presented in this paper focuses on THD_F. THD_F is defined as the root-mean-square (rms) voltage ratio of all n-order harmonic content to the rms voltage of the fundamental frequency.

$$THD_F = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} V_{rms_n}^2}}{V_{rms_1}} \quad (1.1)$$

V_{rms_1} refers to the rms voltage amplitude of the fundamental frequency (also called 1st harmonic), V_{rms_n} refers to the rms voltage amplitudes of the n-order harmonics of the fundamental frequency.

It should be noted that Eq. (1.1) and all subsequently mentioned formulas for THD_F calculations yield the decimal representation of THD_F. This value has to be multiplied by 100 % in order to obtain the de facto standard of expressing THD values as a percentage.

If the amplitudes of the fundamental frequency and all n-order harmonic components are known, it is quite easy to calculate THD_F. A time domain view of a signal traditionally offered by an oscilloscope does not offer the amplitude of each harmonic individually. However, the laboratory landscape has long been shaped by the wide-spread use of digital storage oscilloscopes (DSO). Even entry-level, low-cost DSOs offer advanced mathematical functions such as fast Fourier transformation (FFT). The FFT functionality transforms the acquired signal from the time domain to the frequency domain and displays the amplitude of spectral components as a function of frequency. These values can then be used to calculate the THD_F of a signal.

2. Method

2.2 THD_F Calculation from dBVrms, dBm or and dBc

Frequency domain representations of a time domain signal on an oscilloscope usually results in dBVrms, dBm or dBc measurements that can not directly be used in Eq. (1.1).

2.2.1 THD_F from dBVrms

Measurements in dBVrms can be converted into root-mean-square voltage (Vrms), quite easily:

$$V_{rms} = 10^{(dBVrms/20)} \quad (2.1)$$

Substituting each Vrms_n term in Eq. (1.1) yields the following equation:

$$THD_F = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (10^{(dBVrms_n/20)})^2}}{10^{(dBVrms_1/20)}} \quad (2.2)$$

Where dBVrms₁ is the amplitude of the fundamental frequency (= 1st harmonic) in dBVrms and dBVrms_n is the amplitude of all subsequent n-order harmonics in dBVrms.

2.2.2 THD_F from dBm

For values given in dBm, the rms voltage can be calculated as follows:

$$V_{rms} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{Z}{1000}\right)} \cdot 10^{(P_{dBm}/20)} \quad (2.3)$$

Where Z is the system impedance and P_{dBm} is the power of the harmonic in dBm and V_{rms} is the rms Voltage. For a typical system impedance of 50 Ohms, the square root term is approximately 0.2236.

Combining Eq. (1.1) with Eq. (2.3), yields the following equations to calculate THD_F from the spectral power of n-order harmonics in dBm directly:

$$THD_F = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{Z}{1000}\right)} * 10^{(P_n/20)}\right)^2}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{Z}{1000}\right)} * 10^{(P_1/20)}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$THD_F = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (0.2236 * 10^{(P_n/20)})^2}}{0.2236 * 10^{(P_1/20)}} \quad (2.5)$$

Where P_n is the power of the n-order harmonic in dBm, P₁ is the power of the fundamental frequency in dBm. Eq. (2.5) is the simplified version of equation 2.4 for a system impedance of 50 Ohms.

2.2.3 THD_F from dBc

Some oscilloscopes are also capable of displaying and automatically tracking spectral power in a unit called *decibels relative to the carrier* (dBc). The fundamental frequency is used as a reference for the 0 dBc point and all subsequent power readings are displayed relative to this reference point.

$$dBc = 10 \log\left(\frac{P_n}{P_1}\right) \quad (2.6)$$

Where P_n is the power of the n-order harmonic in dBm, P₁ is the power of the reference carrier, in this use case the power of the fundamental frequency. The fact that Power is defined as rms Voltage squared and the system impedance will be equal for both P_n and P₁, the P_n to P₁ power ratio is equal to the ratio of the squared rms voltage amplitudes of the corresponding signals.

$$\frac{P_n}{P_c} = \frac{\frac{Vrms_n^2}{R}}{\frac{Vrms_1^2}{R}} = \frac{Vrms_n^2}{Vrms_1^2} \quad (2.7)$$

Where Vrms_n is the rms voltage of the n-order harmonic and Vrms_c the rms voltage amplitude of the reference carrier or, again, in this use case the rms voltage amplitude of the fundamental frequency.

This property is useful as it simplifies the calculations for THD_F values from dBc values. This is true because the defining equation for THD_F calculations (Eq. 1.1) can be expanded as follows:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\frac{Vrms_2^2}{Vrms_1^2} + \frac{Vrms_3^2}{Vrms_1^2} + \frac{Vrms_4^2}{Vrms_1^2} + \frac{Vrms_5^2}{Vrms_1^2} \dots} \quad (2.8)$$

Combining the expanded form of Eq. (2.8) with the power to square rms voltage ratio relationship shown in Eq. (2.7), results in a very compact equation for calculating THD_F values directly from dBc power measurements:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 10^{(PdBc_n/10)}} \quad (2.9)$$

Where $PdBc_n$ is the relative power of each n -order harmonic in dBc.

2.3 Known THD_F reference generation

Reference signals with known harmonic content (and consequently known THD_F) were needed to test the method proposed in this paper. I elected to use square and triangle waves due to their known theoretical THD_F . It is well known that a harmonically pure, symmetrical square wave has a theoretical THD_F of approximately 48 %. An equally pure and symmetrical triangle wave has a THD_F of approximately 12 %. This property will be proven mathematically below.

These figures, however, per definition assume an infinite amount of n -order harmonic content. In a real-world laboratory setting, the order of harmonics included in the measurement will naturally not be infinite. Values can either be chosen arbitrarily or be predetermined by a recognized standard. 50 harmonics (or 25 if the probability of interference is low) is for instance a recognized German standard when characterizing public low-voltage power supply systems [1].

I arbitrarily decided to consider 5 and 10 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency and compare the results.

2.3.1 Square Wave

An ideal, harmonically pure square wave can be represented as the infinite sum of sinusoidal waves. The Fourier series for such a square wave is as follows [2]:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \sin(n\pi t) \quad (2.10)$$

For a square wave of a particular frequency the harmonic composition can be represented mathematically as follows:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \sin(n\omega t) \quad (2.11)$$

Where n stands for the harmonic number, ω is the angular frequency in radians per second ($2\pi f$) and t represents time.

If written in it's expanded form, the relative amplitudes of all harmonic components immediately become apparent:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} (\sin(\omega t) + \frac{1}{3} \sin(3\omega t) + \frac{1}{5} \sin(5\omega t) \dots) \quad (2.12)$$

The properties of Eq. (2.12) also highlight the fact that an ideal square wave only contains odd-order harmonics besides the fundamental frequency.

The theoretical THD_F of a square wave containing an infinite amount of harmonics can be determined as follows:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^2} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2}{8} - 1} \approx 0.48342 \quad (2.13)$$

The expected THD_F of an ideal square wave is approximately 48.34 %.

To determine the theoretical THD_F of a square wave containing only the first 5 and 10 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency, n was limited to 11 and 21 respectively:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{11} \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^2} \approx 0.43832 \quad (2.14)$$

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{21} \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^2} \approx 0.45933 \quad (2.15)$$

A square wave limited to the first 5 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency has a theoretical THD_F of approx. 43.83 % (Eq. 2.14). For 10 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency this value is expected to increase to a THD_F of approx. 45.93 % (Eq. 2.15).

2.3.2 Triangle wave

A triangle wave made up solely by sinusoidal waves can be represented as follows [3]:

$$\frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{(n-1)/2}}{n^2} \sin(n\pi t) \quad (2.16)$$

The Fourier series for a symmetrical triangle wave is essentially the indefinite integral of the Fourier series for a square wave. However, the sine representation instead of the cosine version was chosen here.

The expected THD_F for a pure, symmetrical triangle wave can be calculated as follows:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{\infty} \left(\frac{-1^{(n-1)/2}}{n^2}\right)^2} \approx 0.12115 \quad (2.17)$$

The theoretical THD_F of a triangle wave is approximately 12.11 %.

To determine the theoretical THD_F of a triangle wave containing only the first 5 and 10 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency, n was again limited to 11 and 21 respectively:

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{11} \left(\frac{-1^{(n-1)/2}}{n^2}\right)^2} \approx 0.12075 \quad (2.18)$$

$$THD_F = \sqrt{\sum_{n=3,5,7,\dots}^{21} \left(\frac{-1^{(n-1)/2}}{n^2}\right)^2} \approx 0.12108 \quad (2.19)$$

A symmetrical, harmonically pure triangle wave limited to the first 5 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental frequency is expected to have a theoretical THD_F of approx. 12.08 % (Eq. 2.18). Including the first 10 odd-order harmonics above the fundamental, the expected THD_F value is 12.11 % (Eq. 2.19).

3. Laboratory Experiment and Results

To simulate waveforms with adjustable, theoretically deterministic THD_F values, a Siglent SDG 1032X arbitrary waveform generator was used as device under test (DUT). The waveform generator has a bandwidth of 30 MHz and a sampling rate of 150 megasamples per second. A Siglent SDS1202X-E 8-bit DSO was used to acquire the test signals generated by the DUT and to display the FFT results for further calculations. The DSO has a bandwidth of 200 MHz and a sampling rate of 1 gigasamples per second.

The DUT's output impedance was set to 50 Ohms. It was connected to the DSO using a BNC through-termination resistor and a short (~ 40 cm) RG58 coaxial cable.

Square and triangle wave signals were generated with an amplitude of 3.5 V_{pp} (setpoint value in the DUT). The frequency of the test signals was set at an arbitrarily chosen value of 1 kHz. A FFT was then performed and the spectral content displayed by the math functionality of the DSO. From the frequency domain view, the power levels of the fundamental frequency and the following 10 harmonics were obtained. The absolute dBm values were then manually converted into dBc values. Equation (2.9) was then used to calculate the THD_F values of the test signals.

3.1 Square Wave

The DUT was set to generate a square wave with a frequency of 1 kHz and an amplitude of 3.5 V_{pp} into a 50 Ohm load. To ensure optimal utilization of the available dynamic range, the oscilloscope's vertical resolution was adjusted to 500 mV per division.

Figure 1: 1 kHz square wave used for method verification in time-domain view.

The math functionality of the oscilloscope was set to perform an FFT and display the result over a span of 20 kHz with a vertical resolution of 5 dB per division.

Figure 2: Spectrum of the 1 kHz square wave; Center frequency: 10 kHz, Span= 20 kHz

Figure 3: 3rd to 21st harmonic of the 1 kHz square wave; Center frequency: 12.48 kHz, Span= 20 kHz

The indicated power levels of each harmonic were noted and the dBc values were calculated manually. Even-order harmonics were not observed and, therefore, omitted.

Harmonic Number	Amplitude (dBm)	Amplitude (dBc)
1 st / Fundamental	15.8	0
3 rd	7.3	-8.5
5 th	0.3	-15.5
7 th	-0.2	-16
9 th	-5.8	-21.6
11 th	-4.2	-20
13 th	-7.0	-22.8
15 th	-7.5	-23.3
17 th	-8.8	-24.6
19 th	-10.8	-26.6
21 st	-9.7	-25.5

Table 1: Spectral power of the fundamental and first additional 10 odd-order harmonics of the square wave signal

Applying Eq. (2.9) to the dBc values shown in Table 1 for the first 5 odd-order harmonics after the fundamental frequency, the calculated THD_F is 45.98 %. Considering the first 10 odd-order harmonics after the fundamental, this value increases slightly to 47.94 %.

3.2 Triangle Wave

The DUT was set to generate a triangle wave at a frequency of 1 kHz and an amplitude of 3.5 V_{pp} into a 50 Ohm load. The oscilloscope’s vertical resolution was kept at 500 mV per division.

Figure 4: 1 kHz Triangle wave used for method verification in time-domain view.

The math functionality of the oscilloscope was again set to perform an FFT and display the result over a span of 20 kHz with a vertical resolution of 10 dB per division.

Figure 5: Spectrum of the 1 kHz triangle wave; Center frequency: 10 kHz, Span= 20 kHz

Figure 6: 3rd to 21st harmonic of the 1 kHz square wave; Center frequency: 12.00 kHz, Span= 20 kHz

The indicated power levels of each harmonic were noted and the dBc values were calculated manually. Even-order harmonics were not observed and, therefore, omitted.

Harmonic Number	Amplitude (dBm)	Amplitude (dBc)
1 st / Fundamental	11.4	0
3 rd	-7.6	-19
5 th	-18.2	-29.6
7 th	-24.8	-36.2
9 th	-33.7	-45.1
11 th	-33.6	-45.0
13 th	-35.9	-47.3
15 th	-36.5	-47.3
17 th	-37.5	-48.9
19 th	-44.4	-55.8
21 st	-44.7	-56.1

Table 2: Spectral power of the fundamental and first additional 10 odd-order harmonics of the triangle wave signal

Applying Eq. (2.9) to the dBc values shown in Table 1 for the first 5 harmonics after the fundamental frequency, the calculated THD_F is approx. 11.83 %. Considering the first 10 harmonics after the fundamental, this value increases slightly to 11.85 %.

4. Interpretation and Conclusion

All measurement results and the calculated THD_F applying Eq. (2.9) were compared against the expected theoretical values from sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2. The relative and absolute errors were calculated. The following table shows the results for the square wave experiment:

Harmonics (odd order)	Theor. THD _F	Measured THD _F	Abs. Error	Rel. Error
6	43.83 %	45.98 %	2.15 %	4.91 %
11	45.93 %	47.94 %	2.01 %	4.38 %

Table 3: Absolute and relative errors of measurements for the square wave measurements against expected theoretical values

The absolute and relative errors for the triangle wave experiment are shown in the following table:

Harmonics (odd order)	Theor. THD _F	Measured THD _F	Abs. Error	Rel. Error
6	12.08 %	11.83 %	0.25 %	-2.07 %
11	12.11 %	11.85 %	0.26 %	-2.19 %

Table 4: Absolute and relative errors of measurements for the triangle wave measurements against theoretical values

The absolute and relative error for the triangle wave experiment are considerably better than expected. Especially considering the simplicity of the test setup. It could be argued that the significantly higher absolute and relative errors for the square wave experiment shown in Table 3 can be attributed to the test signal itself. A closer look at the power levels shown in Table 1 point to some noticeable problems; The 11th and 21st harmonics appear to have higher amplitudes than their preceding odd-order harmonics. This is not consistent with the expected amplitude progression as shown in Eq. (2.11) and Eq. (2.12) respectively.

It should be noted that the amplitudes of the test signals were intently set in a way to utilize the maximum dynamic range of the oscilloscope's analog-to-digital converter (ADC). The dynamic range of a DSO can theoretically be calculated using the following equation [4]:

$$dBFS = 20 \log(2^{1-n}) \quad (4.1)$$

Where n is the number of (effective) bits of the ADC and dBFS is the available dynamic range of the instrument expressed as decibels relative to full scale.

Most oscilloscopes use 8-bit ADCs, which corresponds to a theoretical dynamic range of approx. -42 dBFS. For a 10-bit or 12-bit ADC the theoretical dynamic ranges are approx. -54 dBFS or -66 dBFS respectively.

The maximum, available dynamic range needs to be considered carefully when setting up the vertical scale of the oscilloscope for THD_F measurements using the method shown in this paper. If the vertical scale is set too high, the available dynamic range will deteriorate drastically. On the other side, setting the vertical scale too low will also impede measurements due to clipping.

Available dynamic range also defines the limit of the method presented in this paper. Harmonics with relative amplitudes below the available dynamic range in respect to the fundamental can naturally not be measured and consequently not be included in subsequent calculations. Furthermore, the maximum theoretical dynamic range

described in Eq. (4.1) is true only for an ideal n -bit ADC. Primarily due to noise and distortion, the effective number of bits (ENOB) and, therefore, the available dynamic range is intrinsically lower [5].

Consequently, I suggest not to use the method shown in conjunction with 8-bit oscilloscopes if harmonic content with amplitudes below 30 dBc is expected to be present in the measured signal. Assuming progressively decaying amplitudes of harmonic content, this method should not be used for THD_F values below 3.2 %.

If higher resolution oscilloscopes (e.g. 10-/12-bit) or ENOB-enhancing acquisition modes are used, much lower THD_F values could be measured.

It can be concluded that the method presented in this paper offers a reliable approach to THD_F characterization using a common digital storage oscilloscope with FFT capabilities if care is taken to not exceed the dynamic range of the instrument.

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